

Permanently marking *Sphodros rufipes* pursewebs for long term monitoring on Tuckernuck Island

Andrew Mckenna-Foster, Cheryl Beaton, and Molly Hukari
Maria Mitchell Association, 4 Vestal St. Nantucket, MA 02554

ABSTRACT

Tuckernuck Island, Massachusetts is home to one of the densest colonies of the purseweb spider *Sphodros rufipes*, on the east coast. During the 2009 summer, we counted and marked pursewebs in 27 square meter quadrats on Tuckernuck. Quadrat locations were carefully recorded so that they can be revisited over the next decade to monitor individual *S. rufipes* spiders within the larger colony. The goal is to record how long a spider stays in one place, how web densities change spatially, and determine average individual longevity. Our quadrats indicate that the colony is much denser than previously thought with $2.9 \pm .0.8$ webs per square meter (with standard error). We also set up a 10 m x 10 m survey plot where we counted and marked every web to record clustering of webs within a large area. This plot produced a density measurement of 0.47 webs per square meter.

Keywords: *Sphodros rufipes*, Tuckernuck, Web density

INTRODUCTION

Since 2006, we have made annual trips to Tuckernuck Island to measure the web densities of the *Sphodros rufipes* population that exists across the island (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008). *S. rufipes* is a very cryptic spider that builds camouflaged, tube like webs that extend several centimeters off the ground. The spiders rarely leave their webs. In 2008, we counted 0.18 webs per square meter (333 webs within a 50 x 37 m plot) on the east side of the island, suggesting that the Tuckernuck population represents one of the densest colonies on the east coast.

Because this spider is usually very difficult to find (and even when a web is located there may only be a few specimens nearby), information on population dynamics does not exist. Our objective in 2009 was to semi-permanently mark the location of *S. rufipes* webs on Tuckernuck so that they could be monitored over the next decade. By revisiting these webs every few years we hope to record how long a spider stays in one place, how web densities change spatially, and determine average individual longevity. To our knowledge, this is the only work of this type in the country and this is the only *Sphodros* species being investigated in this way.

METHODS

We used aluminum tags secured to 20 cm long metal stakes salvaged from used survey flags (Fig 1) to mark webs. We etched the web identifier into the aluminum and placed the stake 10 cm north of each web (Fig 2).

Our original methods called for counting and marking every web within several 10 x 10 m plots near the site of our previous web density work on the east side of the island (Fig 3). We hoped that 100 m² was large enough to show small scale variation in web density (i.e. colonies

within the larger colony) and would be small enough to survey quickly. We completed one of these plots by outlining the 10 x 10 m plot and then systematically marking every web with an aluminum tag. We assigned each web coordinates within the plot with the southwest corner representing (0 m, 0 m). We randomly selected 30% of the webs within the plot to measure and sex the spider (Fig 2). The corners of the plot were marked with two aluminum tags.

Figure 1. Aluminum tag attached to a metal stake. Web numbers and plot/quadrat identification information were etched into the tag.

The 10 x 10 methodology took much longer than expected and was extremely tedious. We found it difficult to survey the entire plot thoroughly and so we changed our methodology after completing one 10 x 10 plot. Our new protocol called for surveying 30, randomly placed, one m² plots on the eastern side of the island (Fig. 3). We marked webs within each quadrat with an aluminum tag placed 10 cm to the north and recorded its exact location using a measuring tape. These tags contain just the web number for that quadrat. We also placed an aluminum tag at the center of each quadrat with the quadrat letter and number etched into it. To place the quadrats, we randomly selected six, 100 m transects running perpendicularly (54-60 degrees) to a 50 m stretch of dirt track that runs through the study site at 149 degrees. The transects are bisected by the dirt track. Along each transect we randomly selected six quadrats, three on each side of the dirt track. We centered quadrats on the transects with the (0,0) corner to the north. We used the website www.random.org to choose random numbers.

Figure 2. From top left, clockwise. A quadrat ready to be surveyed. A metal tag marking a purseweb- both are visible in the center of the photograph, the purseweb is to the right of the tag and its white top is most visible. The flag and metal tag marking the zero meter point from which to measure transects. An opened purseweb- the metal tool in the lower right pinches the web preventing the spider from retreating while the forceps hold the web open to see the spider playing dead with its fangs most visible.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of 10 x 10 plot and quadrat locations. The drawing is not to scale. The numbers next to the quadrats (small gray boxes) indicate the quadrat location along each transect in meters from the dirt track.

Plot and Transect Locations

The southwest corner of the 10 x 10 plot is located at N41.29884 and W70.2451 and extends for 10 meters at 348 degrees and 10 meters at 78 degrees. The reference point to find the quadrat transects is located at N41.29916 W70.24514 \pm 2.5 m accuracy and there is a metal tag and flagging on the west side of the dirt track to mark the spot (Fig. 2). The actual point is in the center of the track. Since there are few permanent landmarks in the area we measured the distance to the nearest, large Pitch Pine (*Pinus rigida*) (Fig. 3). This pine is 19 m from the starting point for the transect measurements at 122 degrees (magnetic). Our GPS unit was only accurate to 2.1 m at the best of times. To compensate, we also recorded coordinates for the 10 x 10 plot, the transect start point, and each quadrat using a GIS (ArcView 9.1) (Fig. 4). We placed the transect start point as accurately as possible on a 2005 aerial photograph (www.mass.gov/magis) and used the measuring tool to mark the location of the plots. These coordinates are more accurate than those from the GPS unit (see Appendix A for all coordinates).

Figure 4. Study area and quadrat locations on Tuckernuck Island. The black square in the top picture is the study area seen in detail in the bottom picture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

10 x 10 Plot

Within the 10 x 10 m plot we counted and marked 48 pursewebs, 47 of which appeared to be occupied (Fig. 5). This is a density of 0.47 webs per square meter. The aluminum tags were labeled with the letter 'A' (i.e. plot A) followed by the web number. Eighty-seven percent of the webs were attached to non-woody objects (Pennsylvania sedge (*Carex pensylvanica*) and Velvet grass (*Holcus lanatus*) and 13 percent were attached to a woody object (pine-needles, *Pinus rigida*, Poison Ivy (*Toxicodendron radicans*). Significantly, one web was attached to the trunk of a Pitch Pine (*Pinus rigida*), which these spiders were thought to avoid (Hardy 2003). We opened 11 of these webs and succeeded in finding and measuring six spiders. The average length was 2.1 ± 0.2 cm and all were female. The locations of all pursewebs in this plot are in Appendix B.

Figure 5. Location of webs in the 10 x 10 m survey plot. The four large circles indicate pitch pines.

Quadrats

We completed 27 of the 30 planned quadrats. We only completed three quadrats along transect E. The average number of pursewebs in a quadrat was $2.9 \pm .0.8$. Seven of the quadrats (26%) contained no pursewebs and the number of pursewebs in the other quadrats ranged from

one to eighteen with a median of two. This suggests there are many more pursewebs in the study area than either our 10 x 10 plot or our 2008 survey indicated. The 2008 survey only found 0.18 per square meter (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton, 2008). The most likely explanation for this is that the quadrats allowed for much thorough searching per square meter compared to larger scale plots. Pursewebs are certainly missed when surveying large areas.

An important benefit of the quadrat methodology is a lower impact on the habitat from the surveyor's feet. A downside is that the quadrats do not show how the webs are distributed on a larger scale.

The most valuable information from this study will come from future surveys of these same quadrats. We recommend re-surveying every two or three years. The locations of each purseweb within the plots are in Appendix A. Appendix C contains figures representing all the quadrats.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project was funded by a generous grant from the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative. We would like to thank Bob Kennedy for organizing logistics for boat trips and acting as driver and mechanic. We also thank Cheryl Creighton, Executive Director for the Tuckernuck Land Trust (TLT), for facilitating our visits and helping in the field. The TLT kindly provided housing and work space for our stay on the island.

LITERATURE CITED

- Hardy, L.M. 2003. Trees used for tube support by *Sphodros rufipes* (Latreille 1829)(Araneae, Atypidae) in northwestern Louisiana. *J. Arachnol.*, **31**:437-440
- Mckenna-Foster, A and C. Beaton. 2008. Preliminary Observations of *Sphodros rufipes* (Latreille 1829) (Mygalomorphae, Atypidae) on Tuckernuck Island, Massachusetts. Report submitted to the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative on March 3, 2008.

APPENDIX A

Coordinates for the 10 x 10 plot and quadrats as well as purseweb locations in the quadrats. The N and W columns are coordinates from the GPS unit, the columns labeled GIS N and GIS W are coordinates from the GIS and are more accurate.

Quadrat	N	W	Accuracy (m)	GIS N	GIS W	Plot Web Number	X (m)	Y (m)	Comments
0 m Marker	41.29916	70.24514	2.5	41.299161	70.245232	-	-	-	
10 x 10 SW Corner	41.29884	70.24506		41.298782	70.245092	-	-	-	
A1	41.29939	70.24478	5.4	41.299366	70.244809	1	0.59	0.54	
A2	41.29937	70.24479	5.5	41.29935	70.24483	Empty	None	None	
A3	41.29929	70.24491	2.8	41.299269	70.244965	1	0.02	0.1	
A3						2	0.48	0.3	
A3						3	0.67	0.39	
A3						4	0.81	0.47	
A3						5	0.75	0.58	
A4	41.29904	70.24531	4.6	41.299057	70.24533	1	0.74	0.52	
A5	41.29903	70.24529	4.8	41.299041	70.245357	1	0.68	0.12	
A5						2	0.41	0.35	
A5						3	0.08	0.53	
A6	41.29885	70.24548	2.7	41.298866	70.245651	1	0.08	0.02	
A6						2	0.1	0.12	
A6						3	0.05	0.4	
A6						4	0.34	0.35	
A6						5	0.54	0.44	
A6						6	0.18	0.51	
A6						7	0.47	0.59	
A6						8	0.19	0.68	
A6						9	0.38	0.77	
A6						10	0.53	0.69	
A6						11	0.1	0.63	
A6						12	0.2	0.8	
A6						13	0.27	1	
A6						14	0.9	0.76	
A6						15	0.68	0.85	
A6						16	0.52	0.8	
A6						17	0.28	0.54	
A6						18	0.52	0.71	
A6						19	0.82	1.1	At edge of quadrat
B1	41.2993	70.24496	4.5	41.299285	70.244916	1	0.16	0.74	
B1						2	0.78	0.45	
B1						3	0.2	-0.01	At edge of quadrat
B2	41.29928	70.24489	2.8	41.299276	70.244934	1	0.33	0.12	
B2						2	0.22	0.19	
B2						3	0.69	0.76	
B2						4	0.54	0.51	
B3	41.29916	70.24513	-	41.299148	70.245162	Empty	None	None	
B4	41.29892	70.24537	4.1	41.298962	70.245471	Empty	None	None	
B5	41.2989	70.24542	2.9	41.298938	70.245519	1	0.22	0.59	
B5						2	0.8	0.72	

B6	41.29884	70.24547	2.5	41.298892	70.245579	1	0.29	0.4
B6						2	0.13	0.01
B6						3	0.73	0.83
B6						4	0.71	0.08
B6						5	0.57	0.36
B6						6	0.61	0.19
C1	41.29935	70.24472	2.1	41.299326	70.24479	Empty	None	None
C2	41.29923	70.24483	2.1	41.299211	70.244988	Empty	None	None
C3	41.29917	70.24503	2.1	41.299155	70.24509	1	0.83	0.28
C3						2	0.19	0.54
C3						3	0.36	0.84
C3						4	0.27	0.7
C4	41.29913	70.24512	2.5	41.299097	70.245186	Empty	None	None
C5	41.29906	70.24519	2.5	41.299058	70.245245	1	0.88	0.87
C6	41.29902	70.24521	2.4	41.299032	70.245303	1	0.55	0.59
C6						2	0.86	0.94
C6						3	0.71	0.04
C6						4	0.67	0.27
C6						5	0.88	0.26
C6						6	0.19	0.91
D1	41.29939	70.24465	2.3	41.299334	70.244654	1	0.48	0.72
D2	41.29928	70.24476	3.8	41.299255	70.244767	1	0.16	0.75
D2						2	0.57	0.93
D3	41.29918	70.24483	3.8	41.299176	70.244881	1	0.15	0.66
D3						2	0.55	0.07
D3						3	0.94	0.27
D3						4	0.94	0.33
D3						5	0.64	0.45
D3						6	0.14	0.41
D3						7	0.28	0.48
D3						8	0.39	0.56
D3						9	0.71	0.29
D4	41.29903	70.245	4	41.299034	70.245096	Empty	None	None
D5	41.29894	70.24511	2.7	41.298967	70.245222	1	0.32	0.2
D6	41.29878	70.24531	2.6	41.298831	70.245465	1	0.12	0.16
D6						2	0.12	0.8
E1	41.2992	70.24444	4.2	41.299147	70.24442	1	0.43	0.46
E1						2	0.71	0.05
E1						3	0.44	0.18
E1						4	0.64	0.9
E1						5	0.68	0.83
E2	41.29909	70.24456	7	41.299088	70.244519	1	0.18	0.12
E2						2	0.17	0.79
E3	41.29893	70.24474	5.3	41.298925	70.244804	1	0.9	0.94
E3						2	0.85	0.68

APPENDIX B

Purseweb locations within the 10 x 10 m survey plot

Web #	X (m)	Y (m)	Attachment
1	1.2	6.5	Penn. Sedge
2	2.6	1.5	Penn. Sedge
3	2.2	1.4	Penn. Sedge
4	2.6	1.6	Penn. Sedge
5	3.6	9.3	Penn. Sedge
6	4.1	1.6	Dead Stick
7	4.5	1.7	Penn. Sedge
8	4.7	1.6	Penn. Sedge
9	5.75	0	Penn. Sedge
10	5.7	0.4	Penn. Sedge
11	5.5	0.9	Penn. Sedge
12	5.5	1.5	Penn. Sedge
13	5.6	4.65	Penn. Sedge
14	5.65	4.65	Penn. Sedge
15	5.95	4.65	Penn. Sedge
16	5.2	6.2	Penn. Sedge
17	5.5	6.3	Penn. Sedge
18	5.65	6.2	Penn. Sedge
19	5.8	6.3	Penn. Sedge
20	5.8	6.25	Penn. Sedge
21	5.3	6.2	Penn. Sedge
22	5.2	7.7	Penn. Sedge
23	5.6	8.2	Penn. Sedge
24	5.4	8.8	Penn. Sedge
25	6.75	6.45	Penn. Sedge
26	6.9	5.75	Penn. Sedge
27	6.9	4.25	Penn. Sedge
28	6.9	4.5	Penn. Sedge
29	6.52	5.45	Pitch Pine
30	7	2.6	Penn. Sedge
31	6.4	2.28	Pasture Rose
32	6.63	2.35	Penn. Sedge
33	6.53	2.2	Penn. Sedge
34	6.56	2.62	Penn. Sedge
35	6.85	1	Penn. Sedge
36	7.05	1.25	Velvet Grass
37	7.5	2.5	Velvet Grass
38	7.15	3.95	Penn. Sedge
39	7.73	4.8	Unattached
40	7.62	4.1	Poison Ivy
41	7.4	4.2	Dead Penn. Sedge
42	7.81	4.39	Penn. Sedge
43	7.6	8.7	Dead Pine Needles
44	8.6	1.45	Penn. Sedge
45	9.43	4.8	Penn. Sedge
46	9.8	6.5	Dead Woody Stem
47	9.76	6.62	Penn. Sedge
48	9.46	8.65	Penn. Sedge

APPENDIX C

Figures showing purseweb locations within each quadrat. Greyed out figures indicate that no pursewebs were found in that quadrat.

